

Towards Human-AI Collaboration in Genomics and Bioinformatics

My AI Journey and What's Next

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Presented at [Australia BioCommons](#)

My AI Journey for life sciences: First steps

- Protein function prediction (2011-2013)

Training phase (HPC)

C: Controls the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing classification error on the training data.

My AI Journey for life sciences: First steps

- Protein function prediction (2011-2013)

My AI Journey for life sciences: First steps

- Single-label classifier: image classification
 - E.g. An image is assigned only one class: {"Dog"}
- Multi-label classifier: Gene Ontology (GO) Annotation
 - E.g. one protein could be: {"DNA binding", "Transcription regulation", "Nucleus"}
 - (multiple GO terms assigned simultaneously)*

Expert Systems with Applications
Volume 203, 1 October 2022, 117215

Comprehensive comparative study of multi-label classification methods

Jasmin Bogatinovski ^{a b c} ✉, Ljupčo Todorovski ^{a d} ✉, Sašo Džeroski ^{a b} ✉,
Dragi Kocev ^{a b} ✉

My AI Journey for life sciences: Key Milestones

- RNA tertiary structure prediction
- Breast cancer subtyping and prognosis
 - Unsupervised learning (clustering) and supervised learning (survival analysis)
 - Deep learning and causal-based method
- Preeclampsia biomarker identification (biological network)

- The winning methods for predicting cellular position in the DREAM single-cell transcriptomics challenge (2 data preprocessing methods, 11 feature selection methods and 3 prediction methods)

Tools & Techniques I Use Now

1990s – Early 2000s:
Heuristic & Statistical
Methods

 BLAST
 AUGUSTUS

 MAKER
 Evidencemodeler

2000s – 2010s:
Integrated &
Ensemble Methods

2010s – 2020s:
Machine Learning &
Deep Learning

 SpliceAI
 GeneMark-EP+

 GPT models
 LangChain
 LangGraph

2020s – Present:
Foundation Models
& AI Agents

Assembly is “good”, annotation not so much

8.7 million species

Molecular Function

Biological Process

Cellular Component

- Experimental
- Curated
- Electronic
- not annotated

Number of annotated genes

Bolger, M. E., et.al., 2018. *Briefings in bioinformatics.*

Next-generation genome annotation: we still struggle to get it right

[Steven L. Salzberg](#)

Gene annotation errors are common in the mammalian mitochondrial genomes database

[Carlos F. Prada](#) & [Jeffrey L. Boore](#)

[PLoS Comput Biol.](#) 2009 Dec; 5(12): e1000605.

PMCID: PMC2781113

Published online 2009 Dec 11. doi: [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1000605](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1000605)

PMID: [20011109](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20011109/)

Annotation Error in Public Databases: Misannotation of Molecular Function in Enzyme Superfamilies

[Alexandra M. Schnoes](#), ¹ [Shoshana D. Brown](#), ² [Igor Dodevski](#), ³ and [Patricia C. Babbitt](#) ^{2, 4, 5, *}

GeneWhisperer: Enhancing manual genome annotation with large language models

Xiaomei Li¹, Alex Whan¹, Meredith McNeil¹, Samuel C. Andrew¹, Xiang Dai² and Rad Suchecki¹

Genome annotation

```

>W88|PM1A_21W22|****|Mitochondrial intermediate peptidase
Unknown protein
LRR2|TPS17_ARATH|****|Terpenoid synthase 17 IPR008930
GFW7|RTF2_DIC|****|Protein RTF2 homolog IPR006735
Unknown protein
DQ50|DED1_PICG0|****|ATP-dependent RNA helicase DED1 IPR008930
C1H3|ATPF_NICSY|****|ATP synthase subunit b, chloroplast
7390.1|*-*|myb-like transcription factor family protein
RI96|HSPC1_RICBR|*-*|Small heat shock protein C1 IPR008930
P_002509965.1|*-*|conserved hypothetical protein [Ric
0190.1|****|Calcium-binding EF-hand family protein LENO
9250|CYCLD_ANTMA|*-*|Transcription factor CYCLOIDEA IPR008930
5380.1|*-*|Lactoylglutathione lyase / glyoxalase I fam
RC80|RBM39_PONAB|*-*|RNA-binding protein 39 IPR008111
3225|PUB5_ARATH|*-*|U-box domain-containing protein 5
7980.1|****|Calcium-dependent lipid-binding (CaLB domain)
MPC6|RISB_CALBD|****|6,7-dimethyl-8-ribityllumazine synthase
4330.1|***|Chaperonin-like RbcX protein LENGTH=174
9950.1|***|thioredoxin 2 LENGTH=133 IPR005746
QL95|RR2_LEPVR|****|30S ribosomal protein S2, chloroplast
2580.1|***|plastid developmental protein DAG, putative
NY64|GTR8_HUMAN|*-*|Solute carrier family 2, facilitated
P_003592454.1|*-*|Protein of unknown function [Medicago truncatula]
2280.1|***|Protein of unknown function (DUF1218) LENGTH=174
8837|LRKS2_ARATH|*-*|Receptor-like protein kinase S.2
2128|RAB8_DIC|****|Ras-related protein Rab-8 IPR008930
422373.1|*-*|DUF4283 domain protein [Medicago truncatula]
7565.1|***|ECF1 gametogenesis related family protein

```

Manual curation

BLAST
Basic Local Alignment Search Tool

Pub Med
NCBI

GENEONTOLOGY
Unifying Biology

ECO
EVIDENCE & CONCLUSION ONTOLOGY

c. Functional annotation of the protein sequence

Gene symbol: HSA32
 Gene type: Protein coding
 Organism: Arabidopsis thaliana
 Function: GO:0010286 - heat acclimation
 Evidence code: ECO:0000315 - mutant phenotype evidence used in manual assertion
 PMID: 23439916
 Sequence: MAAYYRWKSFEEEDNRPEKPRRYGVTEMRGPHYSVLQ
 HYSVLSQNLQEIFESMGQFVDGLKFGSGNSLIPKSFIKQ
 AIE.....

a. Protein sequence of unknown function

```

>sequence1
MAAYYRWKSFEEEDNRPEKPRRYGVTEMRGPHYSVLQ
SQNLQEIFESMGQFVDGLKFGSGNSLIPKSFIKQ
MAHEHGYYVSTGDVWAEHMLRSGPSAFKDYVEECKQL
GFDTIELNA=NLEVP EETLLR YVRLIKNGGLRAKPMFA
VKFNKSDIPGRNRAFSGYVPEPRSSFEVDILLIRKA
ERMCEAGADTIMIDADDYCKYADSLRADI AKVIGRLGIE
KTMFEASDAKLV EWFVFKRYGPNVNLVYDHSQIMDLECL

```


b. Human-GeneWhisperer collaboration leading to the curation of gene functions

GeneWhisperer offers a user-friendly conversational system tailored for scientists and curators, addressing the pressing need for software support in analyzing data.

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.03.30.646211>

Science workflows accelerated

Start a new project or continue working on existing ones.

+ Create a Project

Resume a project

Browse AI Agents

All

General

Hypothesis

Research planning

Experimentation

Analysis

Genomics

Protein Design

This crew designs and optimizes protein structures through a systematic process of literature review...

Show more

SyntheticChemistry

This crew designs and optimizes synthetic routes for target molecules by developing retrosynthetic s...

Show more

GeneDrugAssociation

This crew analyzes gene functions and pathways, identifies drug-target interactions, and synthesizes...

Show more

MoleculeGeneration

This crew generates novel molecules by developing precise prompts for AI molecular generation models...

Show more

PatentCompoundAnalys...

This crew analyzes chemical compounds from patents by extracting structures, characterizing their pr...

Show more

Drug Target Identifi...

This crew identifies and evaluates potential drug targets by mining biomedical literature, analyzing...

Show more

DiseaseMechanismInve...

This crew investigates disease mechanisms by analyzing scientific literature, biological pathways, a...

Show more

Unique Gene Finder

Find orphan genes between sets of species using Proteinortho. Useful for identifying unique genes th...

Show more

Gene Whisperer

Gather detailed information for genes and proteins by connecting to various data sources such as NCB...

Show more

Protein Structure Pr...

AI tool to generate protein structure for a sequence (FASTA format).

Science Digital Platform

Brief Introduction:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7326125900549275649/>

Watch a full live demo and hear from some of our scientists who are using the system:

<https://lnkd.in/g7BV-Yxx>

Lessons Learned

AI models are powerful but not perfect

LLMs and AI agents can automate many annotation tasks but may hallucinate, struggle with ambiguous data, or miss biological nuances.

Expert knowledge remains essential

Complex genome annotation requires careful interpretation of uncertain or evolving biological evidence that AI alone cannot fully resolve.

Human-in-the-loop designs improve accuracy

Involving domain experts to review, guide, and correct AI outputs ensures higher reliability and scientific validity.

Designing human-AI collaborative systems

Future annotation frameworks should actively integrate AI capabilities with human expertise, enabling efficient, trustworthy, and scalable genome annotation.

A Conceptual Framework for Human-AI Collaborative Genome Annotation

- Conducted a literature review from Genome annotation, manual curation and human-AI collaboration.
- Proposed a conceptual framework for Human-AI Collaborative Genome Annotation (HAICoGA).
- Outlined strategies to implement HAICoGA within the genome annotation workflow.

Understanding Trust in Genome Annotation with AI

Which of the following versions of GeneWhisperer would you trust more to assist you in your work?

Attributes	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Transparency	<i>Full transparency:</i> GeneWhisperer shares everything, including the tools chosen, intermediate processing results, data sources used, and detailed explanations.	<i>Selective transparency:</i> Upon request, GeneWhisperer provides details on specific aspects, for example, the chosen tool, the data used, or explanations.	<i>Limited transparency:</i> Only the results are presented, with no access to the underlying process.
Control	<i>Full user control:</i> You have maximum control by manually selecting the tools and how they are used.	<i>Full autonomy:</i> After receiving your input, GeneWhisperer selects the tools and executes the process automatically without further interaction.	<i>Hybrid control:</i> GeneWhisperer operates with pre-defined default settings, allowing you to intervene and modify them as needed.
Accuracy	<i>More false negatives:</i> GeneWhisperer is more specific and might miss relevant information (false negatives).	<i>More false positives:</i> GeneWhisperer is more sensitive and might include irrelevant or incorrect information (false positives).	
Confidence	<i>Always:</i> GeneWhisperer always expresses its confidence level alongside results.	<i>On demand:</i> GeneWhisperer doesn't report confidence levels, but you can request them.	<i>None:</i> GeneWhisperer presents results without any indication of confidence.

	Version 1	Version 2	Version 3
Transparency	<i>Selective transparency:</i> Upon request, GeneWhisperer provides details on specific aspects, for example, the chosen tool, the data used, or explanations.	<i>Limited transparency:</i> Only the final results are presented, with no access to the underlying process.	<i>Full transparency:</i> GeneWhisperer shares everything, including the tools chosen, intermediate processing results, data sources used, and detailed explanations.
Control	<i>Full user control:</i> You have maximum control by manually selecting the tools and how they are used.	<i>Full autonomy:</i> After receiving your input, GeneWhisperer selects the tools and executes the process automatically without further interaction.	<i>Hybrid control:</i> GeneWhisperer operates with pre-defined default settings, allowing you to intervene and modify them as needed.
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Figure 1: Design attributes and levels for conjoint analysis. Levels represent the design options within each attribute and example of the comparison between concepts presented to participants.

Understanding Trust in Genome Annotation with AI

Figure 2: Relative importance of attributes for trust in GeneWhisperer

Figure 3: Relative importance of levels for trust in GeneWhisperer

What's next

System Development

Use case study

Agent System Evaluation

Acknowledgement

Alex Whan
Meredith McNeil
Sam Andrew
Rad Suchecki
Sonali Majumdar
Xiang Dai
Melanie McGraph
Patrick Cooper
Andreas Duenser
Jessica Irons

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Selected Reference

Xiaomei Li, Alex Whan, Meredith McNeil, Samuel C. Andrew, Xiang Dai, Cecile Paris and Rad Suhecki. GeneWhisperer: Enhancing manual genome annotation with large language models. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.03.30.646211>.

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Melanie McGraph, Patrick Cooper, Andreas Duenser, Jessica Irons, Xiaomei Li, Rad Suhecki, (2025). A Novel Method for Trust-Sensitive Design: Applying Conjoint Analysis to Machine-Assisted Genome Annotation. Proceedings of the Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. Published April 26th, 2025. ACM.